

Table S1. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) between physicochemical properties of cultivation substrate and agronomic performance of *Pleurotus ostreatus* mushroom.

Variable		Agronomic performance of <i>Pleurotus ostreatus</i> mushroom								
		Days taken for mycelia to fully colonize substrate	Days taken for primordia initiation from fully colonized substrate	Days taken to complete first flush growth	Stipe length	Pileus diameter	Fresh weight of fruiting bodies	Number of total fruiting bodies	Number of effective fruiting bodies	Biological efficiency
Physicochemical properties of cultivation substrate	Wet bulk density	0.346	0.307	0.385	0.521	0.844**	0.286	-0.190	-0.109	0.137
	Particle density	0.205	0.380	0.502	0.295	0.710*	0.649	-0.396	-0.320	0.171
	Porosity	-0.086	-0.211	-0.135	-0.534	-0.228	0.274	-0.192	-0.178	0.089
	pH	-0.505	0.096	-0.167	0.124	-0.749*	-0.030	0.478	0.264	-0.039
	Moisture content	0.190	0.293	0.227	0.624	0.397	0.261	-0.234	-0.263	0.201
	Ash content	0.095	0.033	0.062	0.247	-0.051	-0.098	0.557	0.653	0.011
	Volatile solids content	-0.095	-0.033	-0.062	-0.247	0.051	0.098	-0.557	-0.653	-0.011
	Nitrogen	-0.101	0.218	0.201	0.246	-0.300	0.028	0.593	0.637	-0.142
	Phosphorus	0.011	0.072	0.049	0.416	-0.129	-0.161	0.455	0.497	0.112
	Potassium	0.112	-0.590	-0.580	-0.208	-0.492	-0.369	0.651	0.675*	0.220
	Calcium	-0.194	0.214	0.137	0.338	-0.320	-0.312	0.322	0.368	-0.092
	Magnesium	-0.203	0.079	-0.012	0.308	-0.345	-0.341	0.454	0.464	0.023
	Iron	0.731*	-0.470	-0.157	-0.211	0.059	-0.216	0.300	0.511	-0.140
	Zinc	0.333	-0.530	-0.453	-0.097	0.138	0.358	0.638	0.639	0.555
	Carbon	0.104	-0.262	-0.265	-0.212	0.359	0.631	-0.257	-0.323	0.569
	Lignin	0.280	0.307	0.520	-0.093	0.498	0.484	-0.474	-0.335	-0.240
Hemicellulose	0.761*	-0.641	-0.281	-0.548	0.018	-0.160	0.087	0.315	-0.131	
Cellulose	-0.031	-0.309	-0.429	-0.131	0.168	0.507	0.021	-0.009	0.741*	

Note:

** Significantly correlated at $p \leq 0.01$

* Significantly correlated at $p \leq 0.05$